

Attached pages include information on Dr Damien Howard (Principal Consultant Phoenix Consulting) and extracts from resources Phoenix Consulting has developed.

Professional Background Dr Damien Howard

Qualifications:

Date	Award	Institution
2005	PhD	Charles Darwin University
1993	Grad Dip App Psych	Northern Territory University
1982	Grad Dip Ed	La Trobe University
1974	BA	Melbourne University

Consultancy Work

Aside from projects involving formal research Phoenix has been involved in consultancy projects over a diverse range of human service areas. Particular strengths in consultancy are in cross cultural service provision and innovative project design across diverse sectors. See below:

- ❖ **Development of website that distributes past work by the Phoenix Consulting on remote cross cultural human resource issues. (<http://remote.crosscultural.googlepages.com/home>) (2008)**
- ❖ **Development of implementation plan for health system of Tokelau-a small remote self-governing territory of New Zealand for NZAID (2004)**
- ❖ **Development of training package for NT Juvenile Diversion Unit for service providers working with teenagers involved in antisocial behaviour (2003)**
- ❖ **Review of Aged Care Services conducted for Katherine West Health Board (2003)**
- ❖ **Review of New Zealand aid program to the health system of Tokelau for NZAID (2002)**
- ❖ **Review of New Zealand aid program to the health system of Niue- a small remote pacific island nation for NZAID. (2002)**
- ❖ **Consultancy to Katherine West Health Board in providing counselling services, performance and organisational review. (2001- 2006)**
- ❖ **Research feasibility of establishment of an Indigenous Education Board on the Tiwi Islands of the Northern Territory (2001)**
- ❖ **Developing support materials for teachers returning from bush communities for Australian Education Union. (2000)**
- ❖ **Developing material for website for Royal College of General Practitioners to support GP orientation to working in remote communities. (2000)**
- ❖ **Development of team development materials for cross-cultural, multi-disciplinary health teams working in remote areas for the Centre for Remote Health and the NT Remote Workforce Agency. (2001)**
- ❖ **Evaluation of the Commonwealth funded disability support services in the Northern Territory 1995-1999.**
- ❖ **Consultancy to examine need for and model for a mental health disability employment service in Darwin. 1998.**

Publications and resources on Indigenous hearing loss developed by Dr Damien Howard and Phoenix Consulting

Howard, D and Barney, J. (2018) Minced words: the importance of widespread hearing loss as an issue in the mental health of Indigenous Australians. *Australian Indigenous Health Bulletin* 18(1) Retrieved [access date] <http://healthbulletin.org.au/articles/minced-words-the-importance-of-widespread-hearing-loss-as-an-issue-in-the-mental-health-of->

[indigenous-australians](#)

- Howard, D and Barney, J. (2017). When more than words are needed. Available online: http://www.academia.edu/34036614/When_More_Than_Words_are_Needed
- Howard, D. (2014). Psychosocial outcomes of children with ear infections and hearing problems: a longitudinal study. BMC Pediatrics 14, 65. Available online: <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-2431/14/65>
- Vanderpoll, T and Howard, D. (2012). Massive prevalence of hearing loss among aboriginal inmates in the northern territory. Indigenous Law Bulletin 7(28). http://www.ilc.unsw.edu.au/sites/ilc.unsw.edu.au/files/articles/ILB%207-28%20Hearing%20Loss%20-%20Vanderpoll_Howard.pdf
- Howard, D. (2012). Families as First Teachers (FaFT) Hearing Loss Literature Review: part of the Cross Agency Prevention of Conductive Hearing Loss Strategy Project, a partnership between Batchelor Institute of Indigenous Tertiary Education and Phoenix Consulting.
- Hogan, A, Howard, D, and Yiengprugsawan, V. (2012, May). The Wellbeing of Children with Ear Infection – A Cross Sectional Study. Paper session presented at the OMOZ Conference, Perth.
- Vanderpoll, T and Howard, D. (2011). Investigation into hearing impairment among Indigenous prisoners within the Northern Territory Correctional Services: a report. Available online at: http://www.healthinfonet.ecu.edu.au/uploads/resources/21173_21173.pdf
- Howard, D, McLaren, S, Fasoli, L and Wunungmurra, A. (2011). Dangerous listening: The exposure of indigenous people to excessive noise. Aboriginal & Islander Health Worker Journal 35(1). <https://childdetentionnt.royalcommission.gov.au/NT-public-hearings/Documents/evidence-2016/evidence13october/Exh-025-010.pdf>
- Howard, D, Wunungmurra, A and Fasoli, L. (2011). Too much loud noise stories. Aboriginal & Islander Health Worker Journal 35(2). https://www.academia.edu/36122390/Too_Much_Loud_Noise_Stories
- Howard, D. (2011). When bad things happen. What happens and what to do. This story tells how there can be new beginnings even after bad experiences.
- Howard, D. (2011). Conductive hearing loss and ear infections: Understanding and managing the effects of children's hearing loss caused by Otitis Media. Darwin, NT: Phoenix Consulting. https://www.academia.edu/36122406/Conductive_Hearing_Loss_and_Ear_Disease_Damien_Howard
- Howard, D. (2010, September). When Talking Fails: Hearing Loss and Chronic Disease. Paper session presented at the 14th Annual NT Chronic Diseases Network Conference, Darwin.
- Howard, D. (2010). Inquiry into the high level of involvement of indigenous youth in the criminal justice system. Submission in response to the terms of reference of the Parliamentary inquiry into the high level of involvement of indigenous juveniles and young adults in the criminal justice system.
- Howard, D. (2007). Intercultural communications and conductive hearing loss. First people's child and family review: A journal on innovation and best practices in Aboriginal child welfare administration, research, policy and practice 3(4), 96-105. Available online: http://www.fncairingsociety.ca/pubs/vol3num4/Howard_page96.pdf
- Howard, D. (2007). Group Training Northern Territory Indigenous Hearing and Mentoring Strategy Project. Final report to the Commonwealth Department of Education, Science and Training. Darwin, NT: Phoenix Consulting.
- Howard, D. (2007). Mild hearing loss and occupational functioning of remote Aboriginal workers. Unpublished report. Darwin, NT: Phoenix Consulting.

- Howard, D. and Hampton, D. (2006). Ear disease and Aboriginal families. *Aboriginal and Islander Health Worker Journal*, 30(4), 9-16. Available online:
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/ear%20disease%20and%20Aboriginal%20of%20amilies%20-%20journal.pdf>
- Howard, D. (2006). Conductive hearing loss and behaviour problems amongst urban Indigenous students. Unpublished PhD thesis. Darwin, NT: Charles Darwin University.
- Howard, D. (2006). Classroom Case Study: Cross-Cultural Obstacles to the Referral of Aboriginal to Hearing Tests. *The Australian and New Zealand Journal of Audiology* 28(1), 41-46.
https://espace.cdu.edu.au/eserv/cdu:6524/Thesis_CDU_6524_Howard_D.pdf
- Howard, D. (2006). Final Report. Culture, Country and Family: Wellbeing and Stress among Aboriginal Health Workers. A project funded by the Commonwealth Department of Health and Ageing, RHSET Grants Program. This document includes examination of how hearing loss contributes to stress among Indigenous health workers within health Centres.
- Howard, D. (2005). Industry Training Strategies Programme report. Indigenous new apprentices' hearing impairment and its impact on their participation and retention in new apprenticeships. Report to Commonwealth Department of Education, Science & Training, Darwin, NT.
- Howard, D. (2004). Why we need more Aboriginal adults working with Aboriginal students. *The Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 29(1), 14-22. Available online:<http://ajte.education.ecu.edu.au/ISSUES/PDF/291/Howard.pdf>
- Yonovitz, A, Preston, G, Howard, D and Kemp, D. (2003). Hearing loss and communication disability within the criminal justice system. Report to Criminology Research Council. Available:
https://www.academia.edu/31713774/hearing_loss_and_criminal_justice_yonovitz_15-9798.pdf
- Howard, D. (2002). Family, friends and teachers. Reasons Indigenous children stay at, or leave school. *The Australian Journal of Indigenous Education*, 30(2), 8-12.
- Howard, D. (1994). Culturally responsive classrooms: a way to assist Aboriginal students with hearing loss in urban schools. In S. Harris and M. Malin (Eds), *Aboriginal Kids in Urban Classrooms*, 37-50. Wentworth Falls, NSW: Social Science Press.
- Howard, D. (1993). Knowing who may have a hearing loss. *The Aboriginal Child at School*, 21(1), 27-33. Available online:
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Knowing%20who%20may%20have%20a%20hearing%20loss.pdf>
- Howard, D. (1992). Knowing Who May have a Hearing Loss: A simple speech reception game for use by teachers and parents. *The Aboriginal Child at School*, 20(4), 37-47.
- Howard, D. (1991). Mild hearing loss and Aboriginal children's learning. *The Aboriginal Child at School*. 19(1), 33-51.
- Howard, D., Quinn, S., Blokland, J., & Flynn, M. (1991). Aboriginal hearing loss and the criminal justice system. *Aboriginal Law Bulletin*, 3(65), 9-11. Available online:
<http://www.austlii.edu.au/au/journals/AboriginalLB/1993/58.html>
- Howard, D. (1990). Exploring the educational effects of mild hearing loss on Aboriginal students. Unpublished dissertation. Darwin, NT: Northern Territory University.

Books

2010 Conductive hearing loss & ear infections: understanding and managing the effects of

children's hearing loss caused by Otitis media: a guide for families & teachers. Darwin, [N.T.]: Phoenix Consulting, 2010. <http://trove.nla.gov.au/version/182378662>.

- 2011 Listening, learning and work: improving outcomes in Indigenous training and employment. Darwin: Phoenix Consulting. Retrieved from: [//www.amazon.com.au/Listening-Learning-Work-Indigenous-employment-ebook/dp/B00VUTBIJ2](http://www.amazon.com.au/Listening-Learning-Work-Indigenous-employment-ebook/dp/B00VUTBIJ2)
- 2009 Supporting employees who have a hearing loss: A guide for supervisors and mentors. Darwin, NT: Phoenix Consulting.
- 2006 Mixed Messages: Cross-cultural management in Aboriginal community controlled health services. Darwin, NT: Phoenix Consulting. This book contains two chapters on Indigenous hearing loss; one on the impact of hearing loss on workplace communications and the other on how hearing loss influence governance processes in Aboriginal community controlled health centres.

Other Resources

- 2014 Roll on effects of indigenous ear disease. This presentation combines a combination of formal research and anecdotal information
- 2014 Stories by Murabuda. A story from an aboriginal elder about what helps to keep him strong. Compiled by Dr Damien Howard. © Phoenix Consulting, 2014
- 2012 Staying strong stories. Compiled by Dr Damien Howard. © Phoenix Consulting, 2012
- 2010 Ear troubles through life. Keynote presentation 'Bina together Hear together' symposium. Phoenix Consulting, 2010
- 2008 The Conductive Hearing Loss Story. A DVD that describes what otitis media and conductive hearing loss are, highlights the kinds of social responses associated with CHL and describes what families, teachers and others can do to prevent ear disease and manage hearing loss related communication problems. It can be used in Aboriginal health centres, schools, childcare to help inform Indigenous people about OM and Conductive Hearing Loss. Feedback from those who have watched it indicate that it prompts referrals to have ear disease treated and improves communication in families.
- 2008 Middle ear disease and conductive hearing loss: Understanding and managing the effects of children's hearing loss caused by otitis media. A poster for schools, child care centres, health centres and elsewhere. It describes what otitis media and conductive hearing loss are, highlights the kinds of social responses associated with CHL and describes what families, teachers and others can do to prevent ear disease and manage hearing loss related communication problems.
- 2008 Occupational issues for the many indigenous workers who are hearing impaired. (Speech delivered at the 5th National Deafness Sector Summit, Canberra, 24-25 May 2008) pp 3-4. http://www.deafnessforum.org.au/files/u1/Damien_HOWARD_transcript_0.doc
- 2006 Howard, D. and Hampton, D. Ear disease and Aboriginal families. Aboriginal and Islander Health Worker Journal, 30(4), 9-16. Available online: <http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/ear%20disease%20and%20Aboriginal%20ofamilies%20-%20journal.pdf>
- 2006 Howard, D. Conductive hearing loss and behaviour problems amongst urban Indigenous students. Unpublished PhD thesis. Darwin, NT: Charles Darwin University. https://espace.cdu.edu.au/eserv/cdu:6524/Thesis_CDU_6524_Howard_D.pdf
- 2006 Howard, D. Classroom Case Study: Cross-Cultural Obstacles to the Referral of Aboriginal to Hearing Tests. The Australian and New Zealand Journal of Audiology 28(1), 41-46.
- 2006 Howard, D. Final Report. Culture, Country and Family: Wellbeing and Stress among Aboriginal Health Workers. A project funded by the Commonwealth Department of Health and Ageing, RHSET Grants Program. This document includes examination of how hearing

loss contributes to stress among Indigenous health workers within health Centres.

2005 Howard, D. Industry Training Strategies Programme report. Indigenous new apprentices' hearing impairment and its impact on their participation and retention in new apprenticeships. Report to Commonwealth Department of Education, Science & Training, Darwin, NT.

2004 Howard, D. Why we need more Aboriginal adults working with Aboriginal students. The Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 29(1), 14-22. Available online: <http://ajte.education.ecu.edu.au/ISSUES/PDF/291/Howard.pdf>

2003 Yonovitz, A, Preston, G, Howard, D and Kemp, D. Hearing loss and communication disability within the criminal justice system. Report to Criminology Research Council. Available: https://www.academia.edu/31713774/hearing_loss_and_criminal_justice_yonovitz_15-9798.pdf

School Sport and Conductive Hearing Loss. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/31713779/eartroubles_sport_poster

Training and employment outcomes for indigenous adults with conductive hearing loss. Submission to the NCVET on future research priorities. Available on: https://www.academia.edu/31713785/Training_and_employment_outcomes_for_Indigenous_adults_with_conductive_hearing_loss_Submission_to_the_NCVET_on_future_research_priorities

Information sheets: On-line resources

Indigenous Hearing Loss – A Wedge Preventing Closing the Gap. (Feb 2017). Submission to the inquiry into the Hearing Health and Wellbeing of Australia Standing Committee on Health, Aged Care and Sport.

Aboriginal Trauma in the NT; Transgenerational origins & Collective solutions. (2015). The psychology of Trauma Conference, Darwin, August 2015.

Roll on effects of indigenous ear disease. (2014). https://www.academia.edu/15086520/ROLL_ON_EFFECTS_OF_INDIGENOUS_EAR_DISEASE

Adults with APD and employment. (2014). Based on Adults with APD Chat, on employment issues affecting people with APD and the socio-psychological effects of APD on adults. http://www.tempapd.apduk.org.uk/HTMLobj-406/Special_Adults_Newsletter.pdf

I Listen in Different Ways Than Others But I Am Not Mad, Bad or Dumb. (2013). Auditory Processing Disorder in the United Kingdom 9, 19-20. People with listening difficulties often understand what has been said in quite different ways. Because they cannot rely on their auditory skills they develop other non-auditory strategies to supplement the information that they can hear. <http://www.tempinformationsheets.apduk.org.uk/HTMLobj-241/APDUKNewsletterNo9.pdf>

Improving Quality of Life for Indigenous Australians living with MJD Family support as a culturally recognized, effective approach. https://www.academia.edu/31713776/Improving_Quality_of_Life_for_Indigenous_Australians_living_with_MJD_Family_support_as_a_culturally_recognised_effective_approach

Speaking, Listening and Self compassion. (2013). Auditory Processing Disorder in the United Kingdom 8, 13-14. <http://www.tempinformationsheets.apduk.org.uk/HTMLobj-236/APDUKNewsletterNo8.pdf>

Listening Troubles and Little Kids. By Damien Howard, Lyn Fasoli and Alison Wunungmarra. (2011). Resources developed by Phoenix Consulting and Batchelor Institute of Indigenous Tertiary Education. Part of a project funded by the Commonwealth Department of Health and Aging— Hearing Loss Prevention Program April, 2011. https://www.academia.edu/31713777/Listening_Troubles_and_Little_Kids_Little_kids_with_listening_problems_may

- Submission to NT Inquiry into Child Protection. (2010 April). Retrieved from:
http://www.childprotectioninquiry.nt.gov.au/___data/assets/pdf_file/0016/50119/No76_Damien_Howard_and_Jody_Saxton_Barney.pdf
- Wellbeing of Indigenous workers: What contributes to wellbeing and stress among Indigenous workers. (2008). <http://remote.crosscultural.googlepages.com/wellbeingofindigenousworkers>
- Psychosocial issues of hearing loss. (2008). Presentation on the psycho-social issues of counseling people with late and early onset hearing loss.
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/psycho-social%20issues%20in%20hearing%20loss%20for%20VCS2.pdf>
- Aboriginal Health Outcomes and Hearing Loss. (2007). An information sheet on the widespread hearing loss among Aboriginal children and adults that often results in [poor access to health services and poor health outcomes](#).
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Aboriginal%20Health%20and%20Hearing%20Loss%20v4.pdf>
- Communication planning during change management in remote Indigenous communities. (2007). An information sheet on the need to [plan communication around change management](#) in remote Indigenous communities because of widespread hearing loss.
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Communication%20Planning.pdf>
- Indigenous housing, hearing loss and social problems. (2007). An information sheet on Indigenous housing, hearing loss and social problems.
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Indigenous%20Housing%20Hearing%20Loss%20and%20Social%20Problems2.pdf>
- Indigenous Students' School Behavior Problems and Conductive Hearing Loss. (2007). An information sheet on Indigenous student's [behaviour problems at school](#) and conductive hearing loss.
[http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Behaviour%20 %20Hearing%20Loss.pdf](http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Behaviour%20%20Hearing%20Loss.pdf)
- Poor school attendance and conductive hearing loss. (2007). An information sheet on Indigenous students [attendance at school](#) and conductive hearing loss.
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Attendance%20and%20CHL.pdf>
- Chapter Five: Middle ear disease, communication and management. (2006) In D. Howard, Mixed Messages, 58-81. Darwin, NT: Phoenix Consulting.
http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/mixed_messages%20chapter%205.pdf
- Communication, listening and criminal justice. (2006). A presentation to NT magistrates on Indigenous hearing loss and courtroom communication.
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/presentation%20to%20magistrates.pdf>
- Conductive hearing loss and classrooms: Research, policy and practice. (2006). A presentation at the Australian Teachers of the Deaf conference in Adelaide.
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Adelaide%20conference%20%20presentation.pdf>
- Think differently to avoid disappointment. (2006). Auditory Processing Disorder in the United Kingdom, 6, 12-13. This is an information sheet about how not understanding about the compensatory cognitive listening skills developed by people with listening problems can sometimes lead to interpersonal problems and depression.
<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/think%20differently.pdf>
- Communication, listening and governance. (2005). Available at:
http://www.academia.edu/31713794/Communication_Listening_and_Governance_Communication
- Helping children with listening problems. (2005) A booklet for Indigenous families on conductive hearing loss.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Family%20printable%20book%2008.pdf>

Listening difficulties, behaviour problems and ADHD. (2005). Auditory Processing Disorder in the United Kingdom, 4, 12-13. An article about the similarities between social responses related to listening problems and the diagnostic criteria of ADHD.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Behaviour,%20Listening%20and%20ADHD%20march%202006.doc>

Otitis media and conductive hearing loss. (2005) A booklet for non-Aboriginal families on conductive hearing loss.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/Mainstream%20family%20information.pdf>

Trauma, middle ear disease and the tsunami disaster. (2005). An article on how listening problems can compound the effects of trauma in regions where poverty has led to high levels of middle ear disease.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/trauma%20and%20tsunami.pdf>

Smart kids, dumb classrooms. (2005). Auditory Processing Disorder in the United Kingdom, 3, 7. An information sheet on the stress experienced by children with listening difficulties in classrooms. <http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/APDUKNEWS3.pdf>

Controlling the chaos. (2004). Auditory Processing Disorder in the United Kingdom, 1,5. This article discusses how some people with listening problems cope by controlling their environment.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/chaos.pdf>

School sports and conductive hearing loss (2004). This is a poster on sports and listening problems. It outlines how Aboriginal children with listening problems often perform worse in team sports and how coaches can communicate most effectively with children with CHL.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/sport%20poster.pdf>

The trouble with strangers. (2004). Auditory Processing Disorder in the United Kingdom, 2,5. This article discusses how meeting new people can be difficult for those with listening difficulties.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/attachments/apd%20newsletter2.pdf>

Audio-visual resources: available on-line

Aboriginal employment and hearing loss. (2008). A presentation at the National Deafness Forum Conference in Canberra.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/index.php/audio%20visual%20resources>

Elaine Cox talks about conductive hearing loss. (2008). Elaine Cox is an Aboriginal teacher from Broome. After watching the DVD 'The Conductive Hearing Loss Story', she was interviewed about her own experiences with hearing loss as a child and her work as a teacher with Aboriginal children with hearing loss.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/index.php/audio%20visual%20resources>

Equity, access and Aboriginal hearing loss. (2008). A presentation at the NTCOSS conference in Darwin. An overview of the impact of Aboriginal hearing loss on participation in education, health care and employment.

<http://www.eartroubles.com/index.php/audio%20visual%20resources>

Internet Sites

Educational, social and occupational outcomes of Hearing Loss

- www.eartroubles.com
- <http://www.hstac.com.au/HearThis/>